

Performance Evaluation of Selected Liquid Mutual Funds

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ABSTRACT

Economic growth can be achieved by the development of capital market in the country. Investors can get better returns from mutual funds and they can also get liquidity if invested in liquid mutual funds. Bank fixed deposits is an investment option which offers liquidity to investors. Hence this study aims at performance evaluation of selected liquid mutual funds. For the growth of mutual fund industry, awareness has to be created among investors about mutual funds. Data has been obtained for the top performing liquid mutual funds. For the performance evaluation of mutual funds, Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio are used. Nippon India gives the maximum returns, followed by SBI Magnum Ultra Duration Short Fund. UTI, Kotak and Birla funds are giving better returns. The expense ratio for Franklin India Liquid Fund is very high while Nippon and LIC MF Liquid Fund have the lowest expense ratio. HDFC Fund is highly volatile and Franklin Liquid Fund is least volatile. Therefore risk factor is high for HDFC Fund and low for Franklin Liquid Fund. Hence the returns of Franklin Fund are more against risk factor.

Keywords: - Liquid mutual funds, risk, returns, security, money market fund, portfolio returns

I. Introduction

Economic growth can be achieved by the development of capital market in the country. Mutual funds are good investments for investors as well as the capital market. Investors can get better returns and the money can be invested into the capital market. Bank fixed deposits is an investment option which offers liquidity to investors. Hence this study aims at performance evaluation of selected liquid mutual funds. For the growth of mutual fund industry, awareness has to be created among investors about mutual funds.

II. Research Objectives

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To evaluate the performance of selected liquid mutual funds
2. To create awareness among investors about liquid mutual funds

III. Research Methodology

This study aims at evaluating the performance of selected liquid mutual funds. The paper also aims to create awareness among investors about liquid mutual funds. Data has been collected for 10 top performing liquid funds from the website of mutual funds of India (www.mutualfundsindia.com). The returns have been obtained weekly, monthly, yearly, for a period of 3 years, 5 years and since inception. The data has been evaluated using Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio.

Sharpe ratio is the average return earned in excess of risk-free rate per unit of volatility. Volatility is a measure of price fluctuations of an asset or portfolio. Greater the value of Sharpe ratio, more attractive is the risk-adjusted return.

Formula of Sharpe ratio

$$\text{Sharpe ratio} = \frac{R_p - R_f}{\sigma_p}$$

Where R_p : return of portfolio

R_f : risk-free rate

σ_p : standard deviation of excess return of portfolio

Sortino ratio subtracts the risk-free rate from the returns of asset or portfolio and divides the amount by downside deviation of the asset.

Formula of Sortino ratio

$$\text{Sortino ratio} = \frac{R_p - R_f}{\sigma_d}$$

Where R_p : Expected return of portfolio

R_f : risk-free rate

σ_d : standard deviation of negative asset returns

The Sortino ratio considers the standard deviation of downside risk rather than the entire risk.

IV. Literature Review

N Bhagyasree and B Kishori (2016) have studied the performance of growth oriented equity schemes which are open ended using Sharpe, Jensen and Treynor ratios. While comparing with BSE Sensex, 14 out of 30 schemes have outperformed the benchmark returns of Sensex. Schemes which are diversifying have under-performed. Sharpe and Jensen ratios are positive for all schemes indicating returns above the risk free rate. Some funds have given superior returns.

Dr.V.Rathnamani & Dr. P. Ravichandran (2018) have compared liquid mutual funds with bank deposits. They have analysed 5 liquid funds for a period of 5 years on the basis of risk and return using Sharpe and Treynor ratios. Essel Liquid fund gives the maximum returns.

Prof. Gauri Prabhu & Dr. N.M.Vechalekar have observed that tax benefit and diversification of portfolio are the main reasons for investing in mutual funds. The paper has identified factors affecting perception of investors for investing in mutual funds. Investors from the age group 19 to 55 years invest in MIP funds for consistent returns. V. Rathnamani (2013) has found that urban people are aware of mutual funds. Investment in mutual funds depends upon investment style. Conservative investors prefer liquidity and low risk, moderate investors want high returns and low level of risk and aggressive investors look at only high returns. The study has been done in Trichy in India. Awareness programs need to be conducted for financial literacy about mutual funds.

Ch. Venugopal Reddy (2017) has mentioned that all mutual funds have given positive returns during the period of study between 2011 and 2016. Debt mutual funds are more in demand than equity mutual funds. A study of top five mutual funds is done. ICICI mutual fund has performed well. Birla Equity fund has lower risk than Franklin Templeton and DSP mutual funds. Mili Kar and Parag Shil (2015) have evaluated the performance of 40 debt schemes which are open ended with growth and dividend options. They have tested whether these funds have outperformed Nifty. The study concludes that there is no significant difference between Nifty returns and returns from the schemes.

Vinay Kumar (2019) has studied that there has been an increase of five times in AUM of mutual funds in a span of 10 years from 2009 to 2019. The study attempts at analyzing performance of mutual funds in the short run and long run and performance of top rated schemes has been evaluated. It was found that top rated schemes give stable returns though they might give low returns than some other schemes. Mutual funds generate above average returns mostly in the long run. Geeta Rani & Dr. Hooda (2017) have evaluated the performance of mutual fund schemes ranked one by CRISIL. They have used Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio and Jensen ratio to ascertain and interpret the performance. Tata Equity P/E Fund has given better results than other funds such as Birla Sun Life GenNext Fund. People should be made aware of mutual fund schemes.

V. Liquid Mutual Funds

Liquid mutual funds have different features as they offer liquidity to investors. These are open ended mutual funds. These funds are invested into short term money market instruments with maturity upto 90 days. Funds are invested into money market instruments such as Certificate of Deposits (CODs), Commercial Paper (CP), Term Deposits, Call Money and Treasury Bills. Usually liquid funds do have entry or exit load. Liquid funds mainly invest in fixed income securities which have a short maturity period. Hence there is low risk of interest rate as compared to other debt funds.

Table 1: Performance of Top 10 Liquid Mutual Funds

	Liquid fund	AUM (Rs. In crores)	1M %	3M %	6M %	1Y%	3Y%	5Y%	Since Incep tion (SI)
1	HDFC Money Market Fund	7591.62	0.99	2.43	3.91	7.95	7.57	7.49	7.3
2	Aditya Birla Sun Life Money Manager Fund	8422.45	1.03	2.27	3.96	7.91	7.8	7.71	7.12
3	ICICI Prudential Money Market Fund	6093.6	1	2.25	3.71	7.6	7.56	7.55	7.56
4	Tata Money Market Fund	286.88	1.08	2.27	3.78	7.57	5.01	5.99	6.97
5	Nippon India Money Market Fund	4217.99	0.83	2.02	3.56	7.52	7.64	7.58	7.8
6	SBI Magnum Ultra Short Duration Fund	9847.93	0.82	1.92	3.43	7.41	7.56	7.54	7.41
7	UTI Money Market Fund	4898.41	0.86	1.97	3.49	7.38	7.56	7.55	7.88
8	Kotak Money Market Fund	7952.59	0.69	1.83	3.33	7.22	7.49	7.53	7.41
9	Franklin India Liquid Fund	3027.74	0.33	1.67	2.78	5.95	6.82	7.13	7.7
10	LIC MF Liquid Fund	7481.33	0.33	1.62	2.68	5.62	6.61	6.94	7.72

Source: www.mutualfundsindia.com

The table shows that HDFC Money Market Fund gives the highest returns, 7.95 % in 1 year, Aditya Birla Sun Life Money Manager Fund gives 7.91 % returns. For the period 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year and 3 years HDFC and Aditya Birla are giving maximum returns. Since these are liquid funds, short term returns are to be seen. Assets under Management (AUM) are highest for SBI Magnum Fund, 9847.93 crores which enable the fund for more diversification and hence minimization of risk. Aditya Birla Sun Life Fund, Kotak Money Market Fund and HDFC Money Market Fund also have more AUM. Tata Money Market Fund has the least AUM, 286.88 crores.

Chart 1: Performance of top 10 Liquid Funds (% Returns)

The chart depicts that except for Tata Money Market Fund, all funds are giving similar returns. Tata Money Market Fund took a dip in returns for a period of 3 years and 5 years.

Table 2: Performance Ratios of Top 10 Liquid Mutual Funds

	Liquid fund	Inception Date	Mean	SD	Sharpe ratio	Sortino	Beta	Alpha	Expense ratio
1	HDFC Money Market Fund	Nov-99	7.34	0.59	3.35	10.43	0.92	3.1	0.35
2	Aditya Birla Sun Life Money Manager Fund	Oct-05	7.56	0.55	3.98	13.18	0.77	3.13	0.31
3	ICICI Prudential Money Market Fund	Mar-06	7.33	0.52	3.74	12.48	0.68	2.79	0.27
4	Tata Money Market Fund	May-03	4.98	3.61	-0.11	-0.04	0.54	0.27	0.43
5	Nippon India Money Market Fund	Jun-05	7.41	0.47	4.33	17.74	0.81	3.03	0.25
6	SBI Magnum Ultra Short Duration Fund	May-99	7.33	0.45	4.3	14.66	0.74	2.87	0.49
7	UTI Money Market Fund	Jul-09	7.34	0.47	4.14	13.11	0.65	2.76	0.27
8	Kotak Money Market Fund	Jul-03	7.27	0.41	4.63	13.52	0.87	2.96	0.26
9	Franklin India Liquid Fund	Sep-05	6.69	0.24	5.49	8.46	0.33	1.71	0.86
10	LIC MF Liquid Fund	Mar-02	6.48	0.25	4.38	6.08	0.39	1.58	0.25

Source: www.mutualfundsindia.com

Table 2 shows the performance ratios for the mutual funds. Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio show similar trends. Just like the Sharpe ratio, higher Sortino ratio is better. An investor would prefer the fund with higher ratio as the investment is earning more returns per unit against the risk taken. Further analysis of returns vis-à-vis risk tells us that Nippon India gives the maximum returns, followed by SBI Magnum Ultra Duration Short Fund. UTI, Kotak and Birla funds are giving better returns. The expense ratio for Franklin India Liquid Fund is very high, 0.86 of the assets, while Nippon and LIC MF Liquid Fund have the lowest expense ratio, 0.25.

Beta indicates the volatility of the fund. HDFC Fund is very volatile, 0.92. This indicates that the market fluctuations affect the fund and hence it is more risky. Whereas, Franklin Liquid Fund is very less volatile. Therefore the risk factor is less in Franklin Liquid Fund. Hence it gives more returns against risk factor.

VI. Findings and Conclusion

The study aims at evaluating the performance of selected ten liquid mutual funds. Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio are used to analyse the returns. Higher the Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio, the better. A fund with higher ratio would earn more returns per unit against the risk taken. Analysis of data using Sharpe and Sortino ratio tell us that Nippon India gives the maximum returns, followed by SBI Magnum Ultra Duration Short Fund. UTI, Kotak and Birla funds are giving better returns. The expense ratio for Franklin India Liquid Fund is very high, 0.86 of the assets, while Nippon and LIC MF Liquid Fund have the lowest expense ratio, 0.25. Lower the expense ratio, the better.

HDFC Fund is highly volatile and Franklin Liquid Fund is least volatile. Therefore risk factor is high for HDFC Fund and low for Franklin Liquid Fund. Hence the returns of Franklin Fund are more against risk factor.

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